

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 5.2 1st Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report

Public

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1. Summary

The 1st Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report describe all activities planned and performed as described in T5.1 and executed in the first year of the project implementation. This work has been executed through effective and consistent collaboration with other partners, networks and stakeholders.

Moreover, this Deliverable D5.2 is touching issues partly described in Deliverable D5.1 CYCLOPES Community Building Framework and Governance model with a framework and governance structure via which all CYCLOPES community members work together to reach the goals, ambition and granted objectives of the project. As the CYCLOPES project is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) and aims at establishing a Law Enforcement Practitioners' Network focusing on Fighting Cybercrime, the CYCLOPES Community building tasks are most relevant. There are already many institutions, networks and other initiatives focused on fighting cybercrime and other domains relevant for the CYCLOPES project.

2. Introduction

Aside from CYCLOPES' internal LEA community, the project is working to form a bridge between the CYCLOPES and:

1. EU and international organisations, such as EC, EC3, Europol's Innovation Hub, Interpol, ENISA;
2. networks of practitioners, especially ENLETS, EuCB, ENFSI, i-LEAD, iLeaNet, EU-HYBNET and i-ProcureNet;
3. networks and relevant stakeholders related to cybersecurity (SPARTA, ECHO, CONCORDIA) and
4. other research organisations.

A crucial part is cooperation with existing networks of practitioners and key stakeholders in the cybercrime area - to synchronise work with them, avoiding duplication and overlapping activities. This synchronisation has to be done with all relevant stakeholders and networks; therefore, within the framework (D5.1), the team defined the practical approach to this work using productivity and communication methods such as matrixes and communication channels.

To effectively cooperate with others, it is expected that partners of Task 5.2 participate in events (workshops, trainings, seminars, conferences) organised by external partners.. Moreover, each external partner (community member) of CYCLOPES (networks and institutions) has an identified Point of Contact (POC), responsible, and accountable, for cooperation. From a management perspective, this reduces the risk of the planned collaboration failing in practice.

3. Community building activities and results: 1st year (May 2021-April 2022)

First six months was devoted to developing the WP5 methodology described in D5.1 (CYCLOPES Community Building Framework and Governance model). As for all activities and events, the CYCLOPES project also had to start the work around the COVID-19 restrictions. In particular, the tasks of community building for practitioners networks and the lack of physically meetings were felt till February/March 2022.

As described in D5.1, CYCLOPES distinguishes between different types of Community members:

- LEA full partners
- Practitioners' Forum
- Practitioners' Networks
- EU / international orgs
- Cybersecurity Networks
- Researchers' Forum
- Industry/SME Forum
- Civil Society Forum

Since CYCLOPES is a practitioners network, in first project's year we focused on the first four types of Community members.

The WP5 activities and some results, accomplished by all WP5 involved partners, relevant for CYCLOPES Community building, are listed below:

1. Establishing and activating the cooperation with several EU organisations active in the European Cybercrime fighting domain: Europol Innovation Lab, European Cybercrime Center (EC3), European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS), European Judicial Cybercrime Network (EJCN), European Cybercrime Training and Education Group (ECTEG), European Clearing Board (EuCB), and European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA), by inviting to the CYCLOPES events.
2. Organising the 1st CYCLOPES Dissemination Event on 20th April in Brussels to present the main project findings to a large spectrum of stakeholders and ensure efficient cooperation between CYCLOPES and relevant partners. The audience was made up of around 40 people from CYCLOPES consortium, LEAs across Europe and representatives from the following networks and organisations engaged in the fight against cybercrime in Europe: Europol Innovation Lab, EC3, ENLETS, ECTEG and European Judicial Cybercrime Network.
3. Presenting the CYCLOPES project during various external events, organized by the following networks and projects:
 - a. **CONNEXIONS** (presentation given on 16th December 2021): The CONNEXIONS project and consortium (including 8 LEAs) aims to develop and demonstrate next-generation detection, prediction, prevention, and investigation services. The CONNEXIONS solution encompasses the entire lifecycle of law enforcement operations including:
 - i. Pre-occurrence crime prediction and prevention
 - ii. During-occurrence LEA operations
 - iii. Post-occurrence investigation, and crime-scene simulation and 3D reconstruction.
 - iv. Multimodal data approach includes Surface/Deep/Dark Web and social media content, data acquired by Internet of Things (IoT) devices, and digital evidence.

- b. **CREST** (presentation given on 16th December 2021): The CREST project is linked to CONNEXIONS as sort of follow up. CREST will achieve its objectives by developing an innovative prediction, prevention, operation, and investigation platform that will build upon the concept of multidimensional integration and correlation of heterogeneous multimodal data streams and delivery of pertinent information to different stakeholders in an interactive manner tailored to their needs.
 - c. **CC-DRIVER** (presentation given on 26th April 2022): CC-DRIVER is about researching cyber criminality to design new methods to prevent, investigate, and mitigate cybercriminal behavior. CYCLOPES is collaborating with CC-DRIVER via it's LEA cluster.
 - d. Laurea Cyber Morning with **ECHO** and **EU-Hybnnet** (presentation given on 27th April 2022): Both ECHO and EU-Hybnnet (12 LEA practitioners) are supporting CYCLOPES from the beginning. The project **ECHO** aims to deliver an organised and coordinated approach to improve proactive cyber defence of the European Union, allowing the bloc to act in anticipation, defending against an attack on computers and networks. ECHO is developing a network through which the EU's Cybersecurity and Competence Centres can be best coordinated and optimized. **EU-HYBNET** (Empowering a Pan-European Network to Counter Hybrid Threats) project aims to empower its network to fight against hybrid threats by proliferating knowledge and facilitating cooperation between industry, practitioners and academia, and by providing advanced solutions for network collaboration and delivering recommendations for training, standardization and industrialization of cutting-edge innovations.
 - e. Present CYCLOPES to 15 **STARLIGHT** LEA partners: The STARLIGHT project is about developing AI tools (Artificial Intelligence) for LEAs to support and enhance their fighting crime and terrorism tools and tasks. Between December 2021 and May 2022 DITSS visited the 15 LEA partners from the STARLIGHT consortium to discuss use case, user requirements and GAP analysis. Cybercrime and Cybersecurity was always a topic and the LEAs are invited to join the CYCLOPES community network.
4. Organising CYCLOPES active participation as accepted speaker and facilitating a CYCLOPES workshop during the European Day at the EAFS Conference from 30th May – 3rd June 2022 in Stockholm.
 5. Creating a leaflet on how to join the CYCLOPES community. DITSS together with LAUREA and PPHS, a leaflet explaining the benefits of joining the CYCLOPES community was created.

All relevant documents related to the WP5 activities can be found on CYCLOPES repository.

CYCLOPES

JOIN THE CYBERCRIME LAW ENFORCEMENT PRACTITIONERS' NETWORK

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GET INVOLVED IN THE CYCLOPES COMMUNITY

The CYCLOPES project builds and maintains an innovation-driven network of law enforcement agencies (LEAs) combating cybercrime. We identify solutions and research activities that help tackle the complexity of cybercrime – whilst eliciting priorities for standardisation and recommendations for innovation implementation and increased uptake.

CYCLOPES increases impact by creating successful synergies with (LEAs), Industry and Academia. This is achieved through interactive Joint Live Exercises and stimulating dialogue on pressing security matters and crime concerns in relevant workshops, webinars and events.

WHY JOIN?

By becoming a CYCLOPES Community Member, you join the CYCLOPES network of key partners (including 11 LEA practitioners) and the existing collaboration efforts with other networks and organisations also striving to aid the fight against cybercrime in Europe. Key partners and networks for CYCLOPES includes: EUROPOL, ENETS, ECTIS, EICN, EACTDA, iLEAD, ILEAnet (Procurenet), CEN and 11 European LEA practitioners from UK, Poland, Netherlands, Sweden, Spain, Croatia, Belgium, Latvia, Bulgaria and Malta, form a law enforcement agencies' network across Europe, combating cybercrime.

WHO CAN JOIN THE CYCLOPES COMMUNITY?

We want to build and maintain an innovation-driven network of European law enforcement agencies combating cybercrime with the involvement of other key stakeholders to share knowledge and expertise. The CYCLOPES Community is therefore looking for the following types of cybercrime-related organisations to get involved:

- EU LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES
- INDUSTRY / SMEs
- ACADEMIC RESEARCH
- JUDICIAL EXPERTS
- GOVERNMENTS / PUBLIC BODIES
- CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATIONS
- CYBERCRIME NETWORKS AND PROJECT CONSORTIA

COMMUNITY MEMBERS' BENEFITS

Every year, 3 workshops will be organised with each workshop dedicated to different domains fighting cybercrime: 1) Cybercrimes affecting people directly; 2) Cybercrimes affecting systems; 3) Digital forensics.

INVITATIONS TO CYCLOPES EVENTS

- 1. PRACTITIONERS' WORKSHOP ON THE TOPICS (PRACTITIONERS ONLY)**
CYBERCRIME - AFFECTING PEOPLE
CYBERCRIME - AFFECTING SYSTEMS
DIGITAL FORENSICS
- 2. ANNUAL JOINT LIVE EXERCISES**
AN OPPORTUNITY FOR THE TESTING OF NEW INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND PRACTICE BETWEEN PRACTITIONERS, RESEARCHERS AND INDUSTRY/SMES
- 3. ANNUAL CYCLOPES SEMINAR AND WEBINAR**

ACCESS TO KNOWLEDGE AND FIRST-HAND ACCESS TO CYCLOPES MEMBERS' MA CYCLOPES MEMBERSHIP PLUS

MEET YOUR PEERS TO DISCUSS AND COLLABORATE ON CYBERCRIME FIGHTING APPROACHES

SHARING BEST PRACTICES, SUPPORTING CASES, EXCHANGING NEW TECHNOLOGIES, AND DISCOVERING NEW INVESTIGATIVE APPROACHES

CYCLOPES COMMUNITY MEMBERS GAIN THE FOLLOWING BENEFITS

HOW TO JOIN THE CYCLOPES COMMUNITY?

We hope you are excited to get involved.

By joining the CYCLOPES Community, you can participate in the dedicated workshops, joint Live exercises, annual seminars/webinars mentioned above. You will also connect and gain/share knowledge with specialists and experts and have first-hand access to information and updates related to the fight against cybercrime in Europe.

After signing up via <https://cyclopes-project.eu> (click on **JOIN US**) or by scanning the QR code in the next page, you will receive a 'CYCLOPES Letter of Cooperation' to be signed by your organisation.

WE NEED YOUR HELP, PLEASE GET IN TOUCH!

We invite contributions from LEAs, Industry / SMEs and Academia / Research, who share an interest and wish to contribute to different thematic subjects in the project.

LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES, SMEs & RESEARCH

JOIN THE NETWORK

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4. Current overview CYCLOPES Community

4.1. Organisational Community Members

In the first year of the CYCLOPES project implementation, the WP5 tasks related to community building were focused on delivering the Community building framework (D5.1) and on adding more practitioners and practitioners networks to the CYCLOPES Community which started with the 11 full LEA beneficiary partners.

By the end of the 1st year, the CYCLOPES Community counted 63 organisations:

1. Practitioners:
 - a. 11 full partners
 - b. 16 cooperating LEAs practitioners
 - c. 7 Practitioners Networks
2. EU / International:
 - a. 8 EU/International organisations
 - b. 2 EU LEA technology networks
3. EU projects:
 - a. 9 Cybersecurity Networks
4. Civil Society forum
 - a. 2 Civil Society organisations
5. Research forum:
 - a. 5 Research organisation
6. Industry/SME forum
 - a. 3 SME's

Each of these organisations is connected to CYCLOPES via a PoC from the CYCLOPES consortium.

5. Upcoming and planned community building activities

The goal and focus for the 2nd year of CYCLOPES Community building will be focused on:

- Intensify the collaboration with the existing practitioners community members (full partners; practitioners networks, LEA practitioners and EU/International organisations).
- Establish significant growth in all different types of organisational Community members:
 - a. LEA full partners
 - b. Practitioners' Forum
 - c. Practitioners' Networks
 - d. EU / international orgs
 - e. Cybersecurity Networks
 - f. Researchers' Forum
 - g. Industry/SME Forum
 - h. Civil Society Forum
- Work on reaching out and adding more individual CYCLOPES community members.

In collaboration with the WP5 partners and close cooperation with other work packages, the following activities, actions and tasks will be accomplished to reach these goals:

- EAFS: booth, presentation, workshop in European Day

- Work closer together with WP2, 3 and 4 workshops, joint live exercise and dissemination event organizers to reach a higher level of cooperation with practitioners and find out their community needs.
- Organise the 1st Webinar : Social Engineering (24 May 2022)
- In cooperation with WP6 more networking via social media (linkedin, youtube) and video materials
- Setup CYCLOPES communication group on ENLETS messenger channel
- Continuous communication (1on1 meetings, newsletters, events) to improve the overall CYCLOPES results and their uptake.
- Keep an eye on other opportunities to involve and/or participate in CYCLOPES relevant networks, events and communication channels.

6. Conclusion

In the first year of the CYCLOPES project, the Community building framework and Governance model was established and the CYCLOPES community grew from approx. 35 organisations (full partners and supporting partners) to 63 organisations. An additional 11 individual professional members joined the community.

As Europe is opening up after 2 years of COVID-19 restrictions, we hope to physically meet new potential community members face2face at upcoming events, where CYCLOPES will participate or be the organiser. Building and growing a practitioners community in the restricted COVID-19 years has been a virtual expedition, which is doable if you already know your peers but becomes more difficult if the contacts are new. The CYCLOPES consortium as a whole of course has it's tentacles already in many Cybercrime fighting organisations that helped and will further help to grow the CYCLOPES community within the years to come.